

Quantifying Serverless Elasticity: The `gumeter` Benchmark Suite

Germán T. Eizaguirre¹, Enrique Molina-Giménez¹, Gerard Finol¹, Carlos Molina¹, and Pedro García-López¹

Universitat Rovira i Virgili, Tarragona, Spain

Abstract. Serverless computing has emerged as a powerful paradigm for distributed workflows, offering fine-grained, low-latency resource provisioning to precisely meet job demands. While workflows often utilize hundreds of concurrent CPUs, existing serverless benchmarking suites frequently concentrate on small-scale parallelism and microservice workloads. Furthermore, these benchmarks typically consider only Function-as-a-Service (*FaaS*) backends, overlooking their natural cloud successors, Container-as-a-Service (*CaaS*). These limitations have created a significant gap in evaluating a crucial feature of serverless platforms: their ability to accurately handle sudden changes in resource allocation, also known as elasticity. To address this, we introduce `gumeter`, a new benchmarking suite specifically designed to evaluate the elasticity of serverless platforms (both *FaaS* and *CaaS*) for highly parallel distributed workflows. `gumeter` facilitates a thorough assessment of an underlying platform using a "fire-and-forget" execution model and minimal user intervention. It leverages a set of comprehensive pipelines that sample various typical scaling behaviors, providing an in-depth analysis of elasticity, execution time, cost, and efficiency. We apply `gumeter` to evaluate the elasticity of three popular serverless platforms: AWS Lambda, Google Cloud Run, and IBM Code Engine. Our results reveal significant differences in elasticity across these platforms, showing that *FaaS* offerings still outperform *CaaS* in elasticity by a factor of up to 6.5x. However, despite a lower performance, *CaaS* can be up to 64.5% less expensive than *FaaS* in specific scenarios, thereby unveiling an interesting optimization space for cloud workflows.

Keywords: Serverless computing · Function-as-a-Service (FaaS) · Container-as-a-Service (CaaS) · Benchmarking

1 Introduction

Serverless computing has seen rapid adoption in cloud computing, emerging as a solution to the operational complexities of traditional cloud models, like cloud virtual machines. By offering managed resource provisioning and setup abstractions, serverless platforms eliminate the need for developers to manage infrastructure or runtime environments. Instead, they can focus solely on application logic while the cloud provider handles server allocation, scaling, and execution.

While Function-as-a-Service (*FaaS*) platforms such as AWS Lambda [3] were the first to popularize serverless computing, the paradigm now encompasses a broad ecosystem. This includes scalable object storage (e.g., AWS S3 [2]), data analytics services (e.g., GCP BigQuery [8]), and other managed solutions. Despite their diversity, all serverless platforms adhere to key defining features [18]:

Managed resource allocation. Serverless abstracts infrastructure management, handling not just individual resources, but dynamically orchestrating distributed resource pools behind the scenes. This is especially useful for workloads with high and variable parallelism, where the number of required resources scales in and out frequently.

Pay-as-you-go billing. Users are charged only for the actual execution time of their functions, with no cost incurred during idle periods. This model eliminates waste and optimizes costs for applications with fluctuating or unpredictable workloads.

Decoupled compute and storage. Serverless separates compute and storage, allowing each to scale independently. This improves efficiency and cost-effectiveness by tailoring resource allocation to an application’s specific needs.

Serverless Computing for Distributed Workflows

The properties of serverless makes it a particularly well-suited paradigm for workloads with dynamic parallelism demands. Such is the case for distributed workflows, where workloads are often intermittent and bursty and resource requirements change dynamically. This translates into highly parallelism needs both within and between jobs.

Workflows specially benefit from services providing computational resources in a serverless manner. We call such services *Serverless Computing Platforms*, as they enable instant resource deployment precisely when needed and strictly for the required duration. This allows matching the required parallelism almost instantly, in a proactive way (as opposite to reactive scaling of traditional cluster services, where resources are (de)provisioned in response to real time workload metrics). Notably, *FaaS* platforms can provision thousands of CPU instances within seconds, making them exceptionally appealing for embarrassingly parallel workloads [17, 25].

However, *FaaS* are not the only cloud services that provide computational resources in a serverless manner. To this day, alternative service types, such as Container-as-a-Service (*CaaS*) (like IBM Code Engine [16]), provide highly similar APIs to those of *FaaS*, but with more control over the provisioned resources and essential, underlying architectural shifts. These services, however, are often overlooked in discussions of serverless computing.

What fits in A Serverless Computing Platform?

To delineate the scope of this work, we first define what can be considered a *serverless computing platform*. This definition remains ambiguous in practice, as

modern interpretations of *serverless* extend beyond original serverless services to include various managed components. In fact, cloud providers have broadened the *serverless* designation to encompass managed services that maintain core serverless attributes. Notable examples include managed cluster services like AWS EMR Serverless [1] and GCP Dataproc Serverless [9], which abstract infrastructure management while offering turnkey data analytics and AI capabilities.

◆ We consider a serverless computing platform that with (1) rapid computational resource provisioning and (2) effectively unbounded horizontal scalability.

An analysis of commercial and research serverless workflow processing platforms [17, 23, 6, 29] reveals consistent architectural patterns aligned with serverless principles: (1) a uniform, scalable serverless computing platform for data processing, (2) cloud storage for data exchange and fault tolerance, and (3) auxiliary orchestration services. Figure 1 illustrates this canonical architecture.

Fig. 1: Segregating Components in Serverless Workflow Processing. A serverless data analytics platform provides a programming framework while abstracting the underlying execution flow. Behind the scenes, it features decoupled storage and compute backends, along with auxiliary services (*e.g.*, for logging or message passing). Serverless compute backends offer unlimited horizontal scaling, adaptive resource allocation, and a pay-as-you-go billing model. Storage backends may include in-memory storage, object storage, or managed database services.

Defining a serverless computing platform is one thing, but reaching a consensus on the "best" platform for distributed workflow processing remains an elusive goal. In this work, we're focusing on precisely that challenge.

Do We Need Yet Another Serverless Benchmark Suite?

Properly evaluating serverless computing platforms requires capturing specific performance details while accounting their specific limitations. The literature on serverless benchmarking is broad [5, 22, 24, 30, 19, 12, 27], including function workflows with modest resource requirements [28, 13, 20]. However, to the best of our knowledge there is no specific benchmarking suite specifically designed for highly parallel serverless workflows with cross-platform compatibility.

Serverless workflows exhibit distinctive properties that complicate their evaluation. They can experience parallelism fluctuations spanning two to three orders of magnitude within job [31, 26, 21], creating dynamic resource requirements that existing benchmarks cannot adequately assess. However, current solutions remain constrained by their focus on either modest parallelism scenarios (typically limited to tens of functions [28, 20]) or isolated function evaluation.

To bridge this gap, we introduce **gumeter**, a comprehensive benchmarking suite specifically designed to assess serverless computing platforms for distributed workflows. **gumeter** enables holistic evaluation through representative workloads, incorporates elasticity-aware performance metrics and integrates cloud-specific cost modeling while maintaining cross-platform compatibility. Implemented as an open-source solution, **gumeter** supports both immediate benchmarking needs and future extensions with both further platforms and user-defined workflows.

The key contributions of this paper are:

- A comprehensive benchmarking suite for serverless data analytics to evaluate performance, cost, and elasticity of multiple architectures, enabling direct comparison of serverless computing platforms.
- A methodology to assess the critical triad of elasticity, performance, and cost in serverless workflow execution, addressing a key gap in current evaluation approaches.
- A detailed comparison of relevant computing platforms, including AWS Lambda, GCP Cloud Run and IBM Code Engine, disclosing important and practical trade-offs.

2 Design

2.1 Measuring Elasticity in Workflow Execution

Measuring cloud elasticity in data workflows remains a challenge, as no consensus exists on a standard metric despite its critical importance. While resource elasticity is not exclusive to the cloud, it is inherently associated with it: since cloud services provide *on-demand resources*, it is essential to assess *how fast these resources adapt* to an application’s needs. However, a universally accepted elasticity metric remains elusive—a challenge recognized for over a decade [14].

Elasticity is defined by three key features [4]: (1) resource (de)provisioning latency, (2) the maximum number of resources that can be acquired concurrently, and (3) billing granularity. However, our definition of a serverless backend assumes virtually unlimited resources and a pay-per-use billing model, inherently satisfying (2) and (3). Thus, we focus on measuring how quickly a backend adapts computing resources to match workload demands.

Isolating elasticity as a function of resource (de)provisioning speed simplifies the problem and enables the use of a more intuitive metric. Building on previous proposals [7], we aim to define an indicator analogous to the physics concept of *elasticity*. In materials science, Young’s modulus—hereafter referred to as *stiffness*—quantifies the maximum stretch a material undergoes under a given tension. Denoting ϵ as the applied tension, and L as the material’s length, we define stiffness S as:

$$S = \frac{\sigma}{\Delta L/L} \quad (1)$$

To adapt this concept to cloud systems, we represent the applied tension as the required resources, C_r , and the length as the resources provided by the system, C_p . Thus, the system’s stiffness at a given point in the application’s execution is defined as:

$$S = \frac{C_r}{\max(C_p, 1)} \quad (2)$$

Fig. 2: **Measuring stiffness in serverless workflow execution.** Assuming resources can scale out indefinitely, we quantify the ratio between resources required by the workflow and the actual resources provided by the system.

A static measure of stiffness alone is insufficient to fully assess a data analytics pipeline. As discussed previously, resource demands vary across pipeline stages, each with different requirements. Therefore, in real-world scenarios, evaluating

the stiffness of a serverless backend requires measuring its resource provisioning accuracy *throughout the entire execution*. We calculate it as the area between the required and provisioned resource curves, illustrated in Figure 2. Let the absolute resource mismatch over the interval $[0, T]$ be:

$$S = \int_0^T (C_r(t) - C_p(t)) dt \quad (3)$$

This represents the cumulative amount of under-provisioned resources. To normalize this area, we define the maximum possible mismatch as:

$$S_{\max} = \int_0^T C_r(t) dt \quad (4)$$

which corresponds to the case where no resources are provisioned at all, i.e., $C_p(t) = 0$ for all t .

Then, we define the normalized elasticity as:

$$E_{\text{area}} = 1 - \frac{S}{S_{\max}} \quad (5)$$

This formulation yields values in the range $[0, 1]$, where $E_{\text{area}} = 1$ indicates a perfect match between provisioned and required resources, and $E_{\text{area}} = 0$ indicates complete inefficiency (no resources were provisioned at any time). E , denoting *elasticity coefficient*, represents a useful measure of the elasticity of different platforms hosting the same workflow. However, since E is highly dependent on the specific resource demands of a given workflow, it is not suitable for cross-workflow comparisons.

2.2 A Representative Yet Practical Workflow Set

Table 1 presents a detailed list of all workflows included in **gumeter**, outlining their functionality, execution plan, and observable insights. These workflows are designed to encompass a variety of typical scaling behaviors, from steep scale-outs (e.g., FLOPS, Monte Carlo Stock Prediction) and drastic scale-ins (e.g., Monte Carlo Pi Estimation, Monte Carlo Stock Prediction) to scenarios with changing parallelism within the workflow itself (e.g., Mandelbrot, TeraSort).

For practical application, we’ve aligned the benchmark parallelisms with the standard service quotas of AWS, GCP, and IBM Cloud, assuming one vCPU per serverless instance.

Table 1: Overview of `gumeter` workflows.

Workflow	Description	Stages	Key Insights
FLOPS	Each function independently executes floating-point operations over two N-dimensional matrices.	Single stage with 200 functions.	(1) Measures the computational power of the platform. (2) Reveals steep scale-out capabilities.
Monte Carlo Stock Prediction	MapReduce implementation of a Monte Carlo algorithm to predict stock variation trends.	Map stage: 10 functions; Reduce stage: 1 function.	Reveals moderate scale-in capabilities.
Monte Carlo Pi Estimation	MapReduce implementation of a Monte Carlo algorithm to approximate the value of π .	Map stage: 100 functions; Reduce stage: 1 function.	Reveals steep scale-in capabilities.
TeraSort	Distributed sort over a 5GB TeraSort dataset.	First stage: 50 functions; Second stage: 100 functions.	(1) Evaluates scalability for long-lasting functions. (2) Reveals moderate scale-in capabilities.
Mandelbrot	Runs several stages, each calculating the Mandelbrot set on a region of the linear space.	Seven consecutive stages with [4, 16, 36, 64, 100, 144, 196] functions.	Reveals iterative, progressive scale-out capabilities.

3 Implementation

We use `lithops` [25], an open source backend listed in the third-party integrations of Code Engine¹ as the central building block of `gumeter`. `lithops` is a serverless framework that allows users to run Python functions on serverless platforms. It provides a unified interface for executing functions across different cloud providers, making it suitable for benchmarking purposes. `lithops` supports various backends, including AWS Lambda and IBM Code Engine, allowing us to evaluate the elasticity of these platforms using the same codebase. For benchmarking purposes, we extend `lithops` with an additional GCP Cloud Run backend and prove its extensibility to other serverless platforms.

¹ <https://cloud.ibm.com/docs/codeengine?topic=codeengine-supported-integrations>

4 Evaluation

4.1 Benchmarked Platforms and Setup

To demonstrate `gumeter`’s utility, we compared the performance of three representative serverless platforms from different cloud providers. The setups employed are detailed in Table 2. We selected a pure *FaaS* platform (AWS Lambda), a pure *CaaS* platform (IBM Code Engine), and a hybrid alternative (Google Cloud Run). We extracted execution time, cost, and elasticity metrics from each to provide a comparative analysis.

Table 2: Overview of evaluated serverless platform setups.

Platform	Cloud Provider	Type	Storage
Lambda [3]	AWS	<i>FaaS</i>	AWS S3 [2]
Cloud Run [11]	GCP	<i>CaaS/FaaS</i>	GCP Cloud Storage [10]
Code Engine [16]	IBM Cloud	<i>CaaS</i>	IBM COS [15]

All experiments ran in the `us-east1` region or its equivalent. We pre-warmed instances for all experiments with three replicas of 200 functions to ensure a sufficiently warm execution environment. Each function was provisioned with 1 vCPU. In AWS Lambda, CPU allocation is directly linked to memory, with 1 vCPU corresponding to 1769MB of RAM. For Code Engine and Cloud Run, which offer more flexible CPU-memory configurations, we allocated 2048MB of memory per function to closely match Lambda’s configuration.

4.2 Elasticity

We evaluate the elasticity of each platform when handling different workloads. Figure 3 illustrates the provisioned CPUs (equivalent to the number of functions) over time, offering a visual representation of each workload’s execution timeline.

FaaS backends demonstrate faster and more stable scaling compared to *CaaS*. At low parallelism (Figure 3a), the primary difference appears to be in scaling latency. However, as parallelism increases (Figure 3c), Code Engine exhibits inconsistent scale-out patterns rather than a monotonic increase in provisioned CPUs. This behavior is particularly problematic with frequent changes in parallelism, as shown in Figure 3d.

Code Engine’s scaling issues may stem from its architecture. Unlike *FaaS* platforms, Code Engine instances are provisioned within a Kubernetes cluster and require a membership protocol for provisioning. This could interfere with the scaling latency of Code Engine resources.

Lambda and Cloud Run show similar performance, with Lambda demonstrating slightly lower scale-out latency. Interestingly, task execution time in

TeraSort appears significantly slower in Cloud Run. This could be attributed to the I/O performance of GCP Cloud Storage, given that a distributed sort involves a data-intensive all-to-all exchange between its stages.

(a) Monte Carlo Stock Prediction.

(b) Montecarlo Pi Estimation.

(c) TeraSort.

(d) Mandelbrot.

Fig. 3: CPU provisioning timelines of each workflow, on the evaluated platforms.

Figure 3 serves as a validation for our proposed elasticity metric, which we depict in Figure 4. As commented before, the elasticity of *CaaS* does not match that of *FaaS*, specially as parallelism increases and becomes more variable.

Fig. 4: Elasticity coefficient across platforms and workflows.

◆ While Lambda and Cloud Run provide similar elasticity coefficients in all workloads, Code Engine delivers a far worse measure. For instance, AWS Lambda provides from 14% to 650% better elasticity than Code Engine, depending on the workload.

4.3 Performance

FLOPS provides an interesting metric on the computational power a platform can provide, as it measures the total number of floating point operations per second (FLOPs) performed in a parallel call. We show its results in Figure 5, where the peak line represents the number of FLOPs at each point in time and the effective line represents the aggregate FLOP per second until that moment.

We once again observe Code Engine’s inconsistent scaling behavior in the FLOPS benchmark. Due to their superior scaling capabilities, Lambda and Cloud Run achieve a higher degree of true parallelism, leading to significantly higher peak FLOPs than Code Engine. This enhanced parallelism also allows all functions to complete within a shorter time frame, boosting their effective FLOPs.

Fig. 5: Aggregate computing capacity (GFLOPs) for AWS Lambda, GCP Cloud Run, and IBM Code Engine.

We also show the total execution time for each workflow in Figure 6. As expected, AWS Lambda overcomes both alternatives in every workflow, whereas Code Engine not only delivers worse performance, but also greater variability among its experimentation replicas - mainly due, again, to its unstable scaling tendency.

Fig. 6: Execution time comparison across platforms and workflows.

Despite these potentially challenging results for Code Engine, its architecture offers valuable features that *Function-as-a-Service (FaaS)* platforms lack. For instance, Code Engine supports instance addressability via the network, a long-standing challenge in *FaaS* [26]. The impact of such features warrants extensive evaluation with specific workflows and metrics. However, since our benchmarking focuses on elasticity, these attributes fall outside the scope of this work.

4.4 Cost and Efficiency

We finally compare the monetary cost of every experiment in Figure 7, based on each platform’s billing model (billed only for memory per second in Lambda, and for CPU and memory per second separately in Cloud Run and Code Engine).

Cost results provide an new ground for comparison between platforms, as the less expensive option highly depends on the workflow. Interestingly, it is at workflows with higher parallelism where Code Engine is relatively less expensive, compared to its counterparts –i.e., in those workflows in which its performance was lower.

These results could be related to a cheaper billing model by Code Engine. As cost is measured based on total cpu time, and not end-to-end execution time, the scaling deficiencies of Code Engine do not influence cost.

Fig. 7: Cost comparison across platforms and workflows.

We integrated both cost and execution time into a single cost-performance metric, measured as $\frac{1}{\$*s}$. The results, shown in Figure 8, further highlight the cost-related trade-offs between platforms. Code Engine demonstrates superior

cost-performance for Monte Carlo simulations and performs on par with Lambda in Mandelbrot.

Fig. 8: Cost-performance comparison across platforms and workflows.

Our findings underscore the intricate balance of compromises when selecting a serverless platform. The `gumeter` metrics provide an effective means to quantify the elasticity of the platforms under evaluation, with Lambda demonstrating a clear advantage in this domain, a trend consistently observed in its overall performance across all workflows. Nevertheless, we also bring to light cost-efficiency features that could be highly relevant for deployments operating under strict budgetary constraints.

5 Conclusions

Thanks to `gumeter`'s comprehensive workflow set and robust metrics, we provide a practical comparison of platform elasticity, a focus largely unprecedented in current state-of-the-art benchmarking suites. Our evaluation offers not only intriguing insights into specific cloud services but also establishes a clear protocol for measuring elasticity in serverless platforms.

`gumeter` is designed for easy extensibility, making it adaptable to various cloud providers and services. To enhance usability, we've integrated a practical dashboard that automates test execution and plot generation. The entire `gumeter` suite is completely open-source, with its source code and artifacts available at <https://github.com/GEizaguirre/gumeter>.

Acknowledgments. This work has been partly funded by the EU Horizon programme under the grant agreements: 101092644 (NearData), 101092646 (CloudSkin), 101093110 (EXTRACT) and 101086248 (CLOUDSTARS). Germán T. Eizaguirre is recipient of a pre-doctoral FPU grant from the Spanish Ministry of Universities (ref. FPU21/00630). Gerard Finol is a Martí i Franquès PhD fellow at Universitat Rovira i Virgili.

Bibliography

- [1] Amazon: AWS EMR Serverless (2025), <https://aws.amazon.com/emr/serverless/>
- [2] Amazon Web Services: Amazon S3 Documentation. <https://docs.aws.amazon.com/s3/>, accessed: 22 July 2025
- [3] Amazon Web Services: AWS Lambda. <https://aws.amazon.com/lambda/>, accessed: 22 July 2025
- [4] Barnawi, A., Sakr, S., Xiao, W., Al-Barakati, A.: The views, measurements and challenges of elasticity in the cloud: A review. *Computer Communications* **154**, 111–117 (2020), <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0140366419319516>
- [5] Copik, M., Kwasniewski, G., Besta, M., Podstawski, M., Hoefler, T.: Sebs: a serverless benchmark suite for function-as-a-service computing. In: *Proceedings of the 22nd International Middleware Conference*. p. 64–78. Middleware '21, Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3464298.3476133>
- [6] Eizaguirre, G.T., Hostau, M., Sánchez-Artigas, M.: Serverless data analytics (finally) bridging the gap: Introducing the ortzi dataframe. In: *2025 IEEE 18th International Conference on Cloud Computing (CLOUD)*. pp. 460–467 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1109/CLOUD67622.2025.00057>
- [7] Gambi, A., Hummer, W., Truong, H.L., Dustdar, S.: Testing elastic computing systems. *IEEE Internet Computing* **17**(6), 76–82 (2013). <https://doi.org/10.1109/MIC.2013.119>
- [8] Google: GCP BigQuery, <https://cloud.google.com/bigquery>
- [9] Google: GCP Dataproc Serverless (2025), <https://cloud.google.com/dataproc-serverless/docs>
- [10] Google Cloud Platform: Cloud Storage documentation. <https://cloud.google.com/storage/docs>, accessed: 22 July 2025
- [11] Google Cloud Platform: Google Cloud Run. <https://cloud.google.com/run>, accessed: 22 July 2025
- [12] Grambow, M., Pfandzelter, T., Burchard, L., Schubert, C., Zhao, M., Bermbach, D.: Befaa: An application-centric benchmarking framework for faas platforms. In: *2021 IEEE International Conference on Cloud Engineering (IC2E)*. pp. 1–8 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1109/IC2E52221.2021.00014>
- [13] Hancock, R., Udayashankar, S., Mashtizadeh, A.J., Al-Kiswany, S.: Orcbench: A representative serverless benchmark. In: *2022 IEEE 15th International Conference on Cloud Computing (CLOUD)*. pp. 103–108 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1109/CLOUD55607.2022.00028>
- [14] Herbst, N.R., Kounev, S., Reussner, R.: Elasticity in cloud computing: What it is, and what it is not. In: *10th international conference on autonomic computing (ICAC 13)*. pp. 23–27 (2013)
- [15] IBM Cloud: Cloud Object Storage - IBM Cloud Docs. <https://www.ibm.com/es-es/products/cloud-object-storage>, accessed: 22 July 2025

- [16] IBM Cloud: IBM Cloud Code Engine. <https://www.ibm.com/cloud/code-engine>, accessed: 22 July 2025
- [17] Jonas, E., Pu, Q., Venkataraman, S., Stoica, I., Recht, B.: Occupy the cloud: distributed computing for the 99%. In: Proceedings of the 2017 Symposium on Cloud Computing. p. 445–451. SoCC '17, Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA (2017)
- [18] Jonas, E., Schleier-Smith, J., Sreekanti, V.: Cloud programming simplified: A Berkeley view on serverless computing. EECS Department, University of California, Berkeley (2019)
- [19] Kim, J., Lee, K.: Functionbench: A suite of workloads for serverless cloud function service. In: 2019 IEEE 12th International Conference on Cloud Computing (CLOUD). pp. 502–504 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1109/CLOUD.2019.00091>
- [20] Kulkarni, V., Reddy, N., Khare, T., Mohan, H., Murali, J., A, M., B, R., Balajee, S., S, S., D, S., S, V., V, Y., Babu, C., Prasad, A.S., Simmhan, Y.: Xfbench: A cross-cloud benchmark suite for evaluating faas workflow platforms. In: 2024 IEEE 24th International Symposium on Cluster, Cloud and Internet Computing (CCGrid). pp. 543–556 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1109/CCGrid59990.2024.00067>
- [21] Mahgoub, A., Yi, E.B., Shankar, K., Elnikety, S., Chaterji, S., Bagchi, S.: ORION and the three rights: Sizing, bundling, and prewarming for serverless DAGs. In: 16th USENIX Symposium on Operating Systems Design and Implementation (OSDI 22). pp. 303–320. USENIX Association, Carlsbad, CA (Jul 2022), <https://www.usenix.org/conference/osdi22/presentation/mahgoub>
- [22] Maissen, P., Felber, P., Kropf, P., Schiavoni, V.: Faasdom: a benchmark suite for serverless computing. In: Proceedings of the 14th ACM International Conference on Distributed and Event-Based Systems. p. 73–84. DEBS '20, Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3401025.3401738>
- [23] Pu, Q., Venkataraman, S., Stoica, I.: Shuffling, fast and slow: Scalable analytics on serverless infrastructure. In: 16th USENIX Symposium on Networked Systems Design and Implementation (NSDI 19). pp. 193–206. USENIX Association, Boston, MA (Feb 2019)
- [24] Rajput, K.R., Kulkarni, C.D., Cho, B., Wang, W., Kim, I.K.: Edgefaasbench: Benchmarking edge devices using serverless computing. In: 2022 IEEE International Conference on Edge Computing and Communications (EDGE). pp. 93–103 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1109/EDGE55608.2022.00024>
- [25] Sampe, J., Garcia-Lopez, P., Sanchez-Artigas, M., París, G., Figueras, B., Jorba, J.: Toward multicloud access transparency in serverless computing. *IEEE Software* **38**(1), 68–74 (Jan-Feb 2021). <https://doi.org/10.1109/MS.2020.3029994>
- [26] Sánchez-Artigas, M., Eizaguirre, G.T.: A seer knows best: optimized object storage shuffling for serverless analytics. In: Proceedings of the 23rd

- ACM/IFIP International Middleware Conference. p. 148–160. Middleware '22, Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA (2022)
- [27] Schirmer, T., Pfandzelter, T., Bernbach, D.: Elastibench: Scalable continuous benchmarking on cloud faas platforms. In: 2024 IEEE International Conference on Cloud Engineering (IC2E). pp. 83–92 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1109/IC2E61754.2024.00016>
 - [28] Schmid, L., Copik, M., Calotoiu, A., Brandner, L., Koziolk, A., Hoefler, T.: Sebs-flow: Benchmarking serverless cloud function workflows (2024), <https://arxiv.org/abs/2410.03480>
 - [29] Tagliabue, J., Caraza-Harter, T., Greco, C.: Bauplan: Zero-copy, scale-up faas for data pipelines. In: Proceedings of the 10th International Workshop on Serverless Computing. p. 31–36. WoSC10 '24, Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3702634.3702955>
 - [30] Tian, H., Li, S., Wang, A., Wang, W., Wu, T., Yang, H.: Owl: performance-aware scheduling for resource-efficient function-as-a-service cloud. In: Proceedings of the 13th Symposium on Cloud Computing. p. 78–93. SoCC '22, Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3542929.3563470>
 - [31] Zhang, Z., Jin, C., Jin, X.: Jolteon: Unleashing the promise of serverless for serverless workflows. In: 21st USENIX Symposium on Networked Systems Design and Implementation (NSDI 24). pp. 167–183. USENIX Association, Santa Clara, CA (Apr 2024), <https://www.usenix.org/conference/nsdi24/presentation/zhang-zili-jolteon>